

Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolated from carcasses of chickens slaughtered in Poland – a retrospective study

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to assess the prevalence of *Campylobacter* on chicken carcasses tested in Poland during 2014–2018 and to evaluate the antimicrobial susceptibility of the recovered isolates. The results were compared to the previous similar investigations performed in 2009–2013 [Wieczorek K. & Osek J. (2015). A five-year study on prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* from poultry carcasses in Poland. Food Microbiology, 49, 161–165]. A total of 2,367 swab samples from broiler carcasses were collected by official veterinarians in abattoirs where chickens were slaughtered for commercial purposes located in all 16 voivodeships (administrative provinces) of Poland. Susceptibility tests against ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, gentamicin, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, and tetracycline were performed using the minimal inhibitory concentration method. *Campylobacter* spp. was identified by culture and confirmed by PCR methods in 1,263 (53.4%) chicken carcasses. The prevalence of the bacteria ranged from a minimum of 49.8% in 2014 to a maximum of 58.6% in 2015. The analogous previous study showed that in the period of 2009–2013, 54.4% out of 2,114 chicken carcass samples were positive for *Campylobacter*. All *Campylobacter* isolates identified in the present investigation were classified to *C. coli* (738 out of 2,367 samples; 31.2%) and *C. jejuni* (525 out of 2,367 samples; 22.2%) and such predominance of *C. coli* over *C. jejuni* being found in each year of the study. Variable resistance rates were observed towards the tested antimicrobials, with most of the *Campylobacter* being resistant to ciprofloxacin (93.1%), nalidixic acid (92.3%), and tetracycline (70.9%). Only a few isolates showed resistance to erythromycin (4.2%); however, there were differences in resistance to this antimicrobial in *C. jejuni* (1.1% of isolates) and in *C. coli* (6.4% of isolates). Among a total of 525 *C. jejuni* tested during 2014–2018, 108 isolates (20.6%) were multiresistant, mainly to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, and tetracycline (94 isolates; 17.9%). In the case of *C. coli*, 185 out of 738 (25.1%) isolates were multidrug resistant, especially to the same four antimicrobials, as with *C. jejuni* (139; 18.8% of total isolates). There was a marked increase in the presence of multiresistant *Campylobacter* compared to the previous study period (1.7% of total isolates tested during 2009–2013), particularly among *C. jejuni* (only one isolate in the 576 previously investigated). The results of this study provide updates and novel data on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses in Poland, and indicate the need for implementation of actions to control and reduce the presence of *Campylobacter* at the broiler slaughter level as well as the necessity to restrict the use of antimicrobials in poultry production.

1. Introduction

Campylobacter, especially *C. jejuni* and, to a lesser extent, *C. coli*, is one of the major causes of foodborne infections worldwide (Kaakoush, Castaño-Rodríguez, Mitchell, & Man, 2015; Tresse, Alvarez-Ordóñez, & Connerton, 2017). Campylobacteriosis is also the most commonly reported zoonosis in the European Union with 246,158 confirmed cases and a notification rate of 64.8 per 100,000 population in 2017 (EFSA &

ECDC, 2018). In Poland, in the same time period, only 874 infections caused by *Campylobacter* were identified (notification rate 2.3). The disease is subjected to registration under the Act of 5.12.2008 on the prevention and control of infections and infectious diseases in humans (www.sejm.gov.pl). However, the relatively low number of cases of *Campylobacter* infection in Poland identified over the last few years, in comparison to neighboring countries suggests a substantial underestimation of cases, e.g. due to still inadequate diagnosis of

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Campylobacter in patients with diarrhea.

The main transmission route of *Campylobacter* to humans is handling contaminated food, especially of chicken origin (Humphrey, O'Brien, & Madsen, 2007; Kaakoush et al., 2015; Tresse et al., 2017). Broiler carcasses are usually contaminated during defeathering and evisceration by feces leakage containing campylobacters from the cloaca (Allen et al., 2007; Gruntar, Biasizzo, Kušar, Pate, & Ocepek, 2015; Rosenquist, Sommer, Nielsen, & Christensen, 2006). Chicken meat is considered to be the most significant source of human *Campylobacter* infections, especially those due to *C. jejuni* (Sahin et al., 2015). The high prevalence of these bacteria on poultry meat and meat products constitutes a public health risk. Therefore, it is important to perform studies on the identification of *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses to assess the risk of infection for consumers.

In recent years, there has been an increasing trend in antibiotic resistance, especially in the simultaneous resistance to many antimicrobial classes (multiresistance) in *Campylobacter* isolates worldwide, which is attributed to the wide use of these substances in veterinary medicine and agriculture (Garcia-Migura, Hendriksen, Fraile, & Aarestrup, 2014; Ge, Wang, Sjolund-Karlsson, & McDermott, 2013). Some antimicrobials, such as quinolones and macrolides, are of the highest concern because of their significance in human medicine (WHO, 2019). Most campylobacteriosis cases are usually self-limiting and do not require any antibiotic treatment. However, the therapy is needed in very young or elderly patients, and pregnant women, or when complications such as bacteremia, reactive arthritis, hemolytic uremic syndrome, meningitis, septicemia or Guillain-Barré syndrome develop (Ge et al., 2013). In these cases, the macrolides (erythromycin) are usually the first-choice antimicrobials, whereas fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin) and, to a lesser extent, tetracyclines are alternative options (Allos, 2001). Thus, the monitoring of *Campylobacter* antimicrobial resistance is highly relevant to public health.

The objectives of the present study were: (i) to determine the contamination of chicken carcasses with *Campylobacter* in Poland during 2014–2018; (ii) to assess the antimicrobial resistance of the obtained isolates; and (iii) to analyze the trends in the prevalence of these microorganisms and their antimicrobial resistance over a 10-year period.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

A total of 2,367 swab samples were collected during 2014–2018 from the carcasses of chicken broilers by official veterinarians in poultry abattoirs that slaughtered chickens for commercial purposes. The slaughterhouses were located in all 16 voivodeships (administrative provinces) of Poland. The number of chicken carcass samples was calculated based on the number of chickens slaughtered in each voivodeship during the years 2014–2018 according to the monitoring plan for *Campylobacter* prepared in the Polish National Reference Laboratory. The samples (swabs from the neck skin and the surface under the wings of the chicken carcasses) were taken directly after the carcasses were chilled as described previously (Wiczorek, Kania, & Osek, 2013). The swabs were immediately transported to the laboratory in Amies transport medium with charcoal (Medlab, Raszyn, Poland). Additionally, the results of the testing of 2,114 swab samples collected from chicken carcasses during 2009–2013, as described previously, were included in the analysis of the trends in the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* in comparison to the current studies (Wiczorek & Osek, 2015).

2.2. *Campylobacter* isolation

The swabs were placed in 5 ml of Bolton enrichment broth (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) supplemented with 5% lysed horse blood and modified Bolton broth supplement with antimicrobials (vancomycin,

cefoperazone, trimethoprim, and amphotericin B) to prevent the growth of non-target microorganisms (Wiczorek et al., 2013). The cultures were incubated at 41.5 °C for 48 h under microaerobic conditions using a CampyGen kit (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK). *Campylobacter* were isolated and identified according to the ISO 10272-1:2006 standard (ISO, 2006). Then, one presumptive *Campylobacter* isolate was confirmed using PCR, as described, and stored at –80 °C for further analysis (Wang et al., 2002).

2.3. Antimicrobial resistance

A microbroth dilution method was used to establish the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of *Campylobacter* isolates to antimicrobials with Sensititre® custom susceptibility plates, EUCAMP (Trek Diagnostic Systems, East Grinstead, United Kingdom) as described previously (Wiczorek et al., 2013). The following antimicrobials were used: erythromycin (ERY), ciprofloxacin (CIP), gentamycin (GEN), nalidixic acid (NAL), streptomycin (STR), and tetracycline (TET). Detailed information on the dilution ranges and cut off values are shown in Table A1. The *Campylobacter* isolates were subcultured twice on Columbia agar (Oxoid) at 41.5 °C for 48 h under microaerobic conditions and then the MIC values were determined on cation-supplemented Mueller-Hinton broth (Trek) with 2–2.5% horse blood incubated at 37 °C for 48 h under microaerobic conditions (Wiczorek, Wołkiewicz, & Osek, 2018). The results were evaluated using the Vision system (Trek Diagnostics). The antimicrobials and cut-off values used for the interpretation of the MIC results were in accordance with the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing and the European Union Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance recommendations (Sifré et al., 2015; www.eurl-ar.eu; www.eucast.org). Multidrug resistance of the isolated *Campylobacter* was defined as resistance to at least three classes of the antimicrobials used in the study (Magiorakos et al., 2012).

2.4. Statistical analysis

The geographical distribution of the samples tested towards *Campylobacter* during 2014–2018 is shown in Fig. 1. The statistical analysis was based on logistic regression models to describe the influence of variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n on the dichotomous variable Y :

$$P(Y = 1|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i)}}{1 + e^{(\beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i)}}$$

where β_i is the regression coefficient for $i = 0, \dots, n$, x_i are independent variables (measurable or qualitative) for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

The maximum likelihood method was used to estimate the model's coefficients. The Wald test was used to evaluate the significance of individual variables. Evaluation of the model's fit to the data was performed using the likelihood ratio (LR) test. The odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals were also calculated. The accepted significance level was $\alpha = 0.05$.

For statistical data analysis TIBCO Software Inc. (2017) Statistica (data analysis software system) version 13, was used.

3. Results

3.1. Identification of *Campylobacter*

Campylobacter spp. was identified in chicken carcasses in slaughterhouses located in all voivodeships of Poland. Among 2,367 samples tested during 2014–2018, 1,263 (53.4%) were positive for *Campylobacter* spp., as identified by culture and confirmed by PCR methods, respectively (Table 1). The prevalence of the bacteria ranged from a minimum of 49.8% in 2014 to a maximum of 58.6% in 2015, and the difference between these percentages was statistically

Fig. 1. Geographical distribution of samples tested towards *Campylobacter* in Poland. Swabs from chicken carcasses were taken from all voivodeships (administrative provinces): dolnośląskie (DS), kujawsko-pomorskie (KP), lubelskie (LU), lubuskie (LB), łódzkie (LD), małopolskie (MP), mazowieckie (MA), opolskie (OP), podkarpackie (PK), podlaskie (PD), pomorskie (PM), śląskie (SL), świętokrzyskie (SW), warmińsko-mazurskie (WM), wielkopolskie (WP), and zachodniopomorskie (ZP). Intensity of the gray background color depends on the number of samples tested. The percentages of *Campylobacter*-positive samples are shown in each voivodeship. Intensity of red color indicates the prevalence *Campylobacter* spp. Color circles show the percentages of positive samples for *C. jejuni* (blue) and *C. coli* (green). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

significant ($P = 0.02$; Wald chi-square test). The *Campylobacter* isolates were classified as *C. coli* (31.2% of the total number of samples tested), or *C. jejuni* (22.2%), and such a predominance of *C. coli* over *C. jejuni* was found in each year of the study, although it was mostly significantly expressed in 2016 (34.5% and 18.8%, respectively; $P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 2).

3.2. Spatial distribution of *Campylobacter*

The swabs were taken from chickens in all 16 administrative provinces of Poland, with the number of samples to be collected being calculated on the basis of the birds' volumes in each of the voivodeships. The highest number of slaughtered chickens were tested in the wielkopolskie (503 samples) and mazowieckie (455 samples) regions, whereas in dolnośląskie and lubelskie, only 22 and 31 birds were

Table 1
Prevalence of *Campylobacter* spp. in chicken carcasses tested during the study.

Year	No. of samples tested/positive (% of positive; 95% CI)	No. of samples positive (% of total number of samples; 95% CI) for:	
		<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>
2014	498/248 (49.8; 45.3–54.3)	101 (20.3; 16.8–24.1)	147 (29.5; 25.5–33.7)
2015	485/284 (58.6; 54.0–63.0)	136 (28.0; 24.1–32.3)	148 (30.5; 26.4–34.8)
2016	458/244 (53.3; 48.6–57.9)	86 (18.8; 15.3–22.7)	158 (34.5; 30.1–39.0)
2017	458/241 (52.6; 47.9–57.3)	104 (22.7; 18.9–26.8)	137 (29.9; 25.8–34.3)
2018	468/246 (52.6; 47.9–57.2)	98 (20.9; 17.3–24.9)	148 (31.6; 27.4–36.1)
Total	2,367/1,263 (53.4; 51.3–55.4)	525 (22.2; 20.5–23.9)	738 (31.2; 29.3–33.1)

CI, confidence intervals with 95% confidence level.

Fig. 2. Prevalence (in percentages) of *Campylobacter*, including *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*, in chicken carcasses tested during 2009–2013 (A) (Wiczorek & Osek, 2015) and 2014–2018 (B). Bars show confidence intervals with 95% confidence level.

Table 2
Prevalence of *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses tested between 2014 and 2018.

Administrative province (voivodeship; number of abattoirs involved in the study)	No. of samples tested/positive (no.; % of positive; 95% CI)	No. of samples positive (% of total number of samples; 95% CI) for:	
		<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>
Dolnośląskie (7)	22/10 (45.5; 24.4–67.8)	5 (22.7; 7.8–45.4)	5 (22.7; 7.8–45.4)
Kujawsko-pomorskie (12)	178/99 (55.6; 48.0–63.0)	40 (22.5; 16.6–29.3)	59 (33.1; 26.3–40.6)
Lubelskie (3)	31/22 (71.0; 52.0–85.8)	12 (38.7; 21.8–57.8)	10 (32.3; 16.7–51.4)
Lubuskie (7)	41/23 (56.1; 39.7–71.5)	12 (29.3; 16.1–45.5)	11 (26.8; 14.2–42.9)
Łódzkie (18)	314/187 (59.6; 53.9–65.0)	65 (20.7; 16.4–25.6)	122 (38.9; 33.4–44.5)
Małopolskie (13)	169/80 (47.3; 39.6–55.1)	27 (16.0; 10.8–22.4)	53 (31.4; 24.5–38.9)
Mazowieckie (18)	455/227 (49.9; 45.2–54.6)	79 (17.4; 14.0–21.2)	148 (32.5; 28.2–37.0)
Opolskie (4)	50/29 (58.0; 43.2–71.8)	13 (26.0; 14.6–40.3)	16 (32.0; 19.5–46.7)
Podkarpackie (2)	59/31 (52.5; 39.1–65.7)	8 (13.6; 6.0–25.0)	23 (39.0; 26.5–52.6)
Podlaskie (4)	76/46 (60.5; 48.6–71.6)	18 (23.7; 14.7–34.8)	28 (36.8; 26.1–48.7)
Pomorskie (8)	136/48 (35.3; 27.3–43.9)	16 (11.8; 6.9–18.4)	32 (23.5; 16.7–31.6)
Śląskie (21)	117/56 (47.9; 38.5–57.3)	25 (21.4; 14.3–29.9)	31 (26.5; 18.8–35.5)
Świętokrzyskie (11)	40/26 (65.0; 48.3–79.4)	16 (40.0; 24.9–56.7)	10 (25.0; 12.7–41.2)
Warmińsko-mazurskie (5)	74/58 (78.4; 67.3–87.1)	26 (35.1; 24.4–47.1)	32 (43.2; 31.8–55.3)
Wielkopolskie (22)	503/261 (51.9; 47.4–56.3)	126 (25.0; 21.3–29.1)	135 (26.8; 23.0–30.9)
Zachodniopomorskie (3)	102/60 (58.8; 48.6–68.5)	37 (36.3; 27.0–46.4)	23 (22.5; 14.9–31.9)
Total	2,367/1,263 (53.4; 51.3–55.4)	525 (22.2; 20.5–23.9)	738 (31.2; 29.3–33.1)

CI, confidence intervals with 95% confidence level.

examined, respectively (Table 2). The highest prevalence of *Campylobacter* was observed in the warmińsko-mazurskie and lubelskie provinces (78.4% and 71.0% of positive samples, respectively), although the number of swabs tested in these regions was lower than in the other geographical locations (Table 2). On the other hand, the lowest percentage of *Campylobacter*-positive chicken carcasses was detected in the pomorskie (35.3%) and dolnośląskie (45.5%) voivodeships, respectively.

Analysis of *Campylobacter* species identified in each of the provinces revealed that in only 4 voivodeships (lubelskie, lubuskie,

świętokrzyskie, zachodniopomorskie) most of the isolates were classified as *C. jejuni*, whereas in the remaining 12 voivodeships, *C. coli* was equal to or more common than *C. jejuni* (Table 2). Furthermore, the percentages of *C. coli* over the mean value for the whole country (31.2%) were found in 7 voivodeships (Table 2).

The statistical model applied in the study showed that all voivodeships except dolnośląskie ($P = 0.36$) had significantly greater odds for having a *Campylobacter*-positive result than the reference pomorskie province, in which the prevalence was the lowest. For example, in the warmińsko-mazurskie voivodeship, where the prevalence was the

Fig. 3. Temporal distribution (in percentages) of *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses during 2014–2018. Bars show confidence intervals with 95% confidence level.

highest, the odds of a positive result was over 6.5 times greater than in the pomorskie province (OR = 6.6; 95% CI 3.4–12.8).

3.3. Temporal distribution of *Campylobacter*

The samples were taken throughout the years of the study, except for January when for technical reasons no sampling was performed (Fig. 3). Analysis of the prevalence of *Campylobacter*, including *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*, revealed that in each month chicken carcasses were highly contaminated with these bacteria. The mean percentage of positive samples tested during 2014–2018 varied from 45.4% in April to 76.0% in December, although only 25 samples were tested in the later month (Fig. 3). When prevalence of *Campylobacter* species was analyzed, a low contamination of carcasses with *C. jejuni* was observed in two summer months (August and September, 16.0% and 15.6% of total samples, respectively), whereas the higher rates of positive samples were found during the spring period, i.e. in March (26.4%), April (25.3%), and May (24.9%), respectively as well as in December (32.0%). In the case of *C. coli*, the peak of *Campylobacter*-positive carcasses was observed during the autumn-winter months (December, 44.0%; November, 43.7%; October, 37.1%; January 36.4%). However, highly *C. coli* contaminated samples were also identified during other months (Fig. 3).

3.4. Antimicrobial resistance

The analysis of the antimicrobial resistance results of the *Campylobacter* tested during 2014–2018 revealed that the vast majority of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were resistant to ciprofloxacin (483; 92.0%, and 693; 93.9%, respectively) and nalidixic acid (474; 90.3% and 692; 93.8%, respectively) (Fig. 4A and 4B). There was no statistically significant difference in resistance between these two *Campylobacter* species in relation to ciprofloxacin ($P = 0.19$), whereas in the case of nalidixic acid, such a difference was significant ($P = 0.02$). Only 6 (1.1%) isolates showed resistance to erythromycin, and 7 (1.3%) to gentamycin (Fig. 4A). Interestingly, no *C. jejuni* resistant to ERY were identified in the years 2017–2018.

C. coli isolates were also mainly resistant to ciprofloxacin (93.9% of isolates over the study period) and nalidixic acid (93.8% isolates), and the percentages of such isolates identified in each year of the study did not differ much (from 90.5% in 2015 to 97.1% in 2017 for CIP and NAL, respectively), although there were statistically significant ($P = 0.03$) (Fig. 4B). A relatively higher rate of *C. coli* than *C. jejuni* isolates was resistant to erythromycin (47; 6.4% and 6; 1.1%, respectively;

$P = 0.00005$).

Furthermore, statistically different resistance rates of *C. coli* and *C. jejuni* to tetracycline (556; 75.3% and 340; 64.8% of isolates; $P = 0.00005$) and to streptomycin (200; 27.1% and 106; 20.2%; $P = 0.005$), respectively were also identified.

3.5. Multiresistance of *Campylobacter*

Among a total of 525 *C. jejuni* tested during 2014–2018, 108 isolates (20.6%) were multiresistant, mainly to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, and tetracycline (94 out of 525 isolates; 17.9%) (Table 3). Such isolates were identified in each year of the study, and in 14 (except for lubelskie and podkarpackie) voivodeships. The remaining 14 multiresistant *C. jejuni* displayed different resistance patterns, including two isolates resistant to all 6 antimicrobials used in the study.

In the case of *C. coli*, 185 out of 738 (25.1%) isolates were multidrug resistant, especially (like *C. jejuni*) to CIP + NAL + STR + TET (139; 18.8% of total isolates) (Table 4). Such isolates were detected in 15 out of 16 voivodeships (except for the dolnośląskie province). Some isolates were also resistant to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, erythromycin, streptomycin, and tetracycline (25; 3.4%) or CIP + NAL + ERY + TET (18; 2.4%). One *C. coli* isolate from 2016 was resistant to all drugs tested.

There were statistically significant differences in the prevalence of multiresistant *C. jejuni* isolated in the years 2014 vs. 2016 ($P = 0.004$), 2017 ($P = 0.001$) and 2018 ($P = 0.042$). However, such a correlation was not observed among the *C. coli* isolates tested.

4. Discussion

In the present study, the results from a long-term monitoring of the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* from chicken carcasses slaughtered in Poland are described. It was shown that 53.4% of samples tested during 2014–2018 were contaminated with these microorganisms, and the prevalence of *Campylobacter* spp. did not markedly change during the study period. The analogous previous study showed that in the period of 2009–2013, 54.4% of 2,114 chicken carcasses were positive for *Campylobacter* (Wiczorek & Osek, 2015). However, in comparison with the previous investigation, the percentage of contaminated carcasses was rather stable during the present 5-year study (from 49.8% to 58.6% of positive samples) and no decreasing temporal trend in the prevalence of *Campylobacter* was

Fig. 4. Antimicrobial resistance (in percentages) of *C. jejuni* (A) and *C. coli* (B) isolated from chicken carcasses tested during 2014–2018. Bars show confidence intervals with 95% confidence level.

observed. This may be due to the fact that no official *Campylobacter* control programs were introduced during this period in Poland. On the other hand, there were differences in the *Campylobacter* species identified in the current and previous studies. During the years 2009–2013, an almost equal proportion of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* was found (576 and 575 isolates, respectively), whereas 5 years later, more *C. coli* (738; 31.2% of total samples) than *C. jejuni* (525; 22.2%) were identified. Such a predominance of *C. coli* over *C. jejuni* was rather stable over the time during the present monitoring program. Several studies demonstrated that *C. coli* was the predominant *Campylobacter* species in pigs, but recent reports have shown that *C. coli* may also be frequently identified in broilers in some countries (EFSA & ECDC, 2018). The present results suggest that *C. coli* may be more common in chicken carcasses than previously thought.

There are no other similar studies related to the prevalence of *Campylobacter* in chicken carcasses in Poland. In 2008, a European Union (EU)-wide baseline survey on *Campylobacter* in broilers was performed (EFSA, 2010). A total of 10,132 broiler batches were sampled from 561 slaughterhouses in 26 EU Member States (MS) and two countries not belonging to the EU (Norway and Switzerland). The mean EU prevalence was 75.8%, including 80.4% *Campylobacter*-positive broiler batches in Poland. *C. jejuni* prevalence was 51.0% at the EU level (53.5% in Poland), whereas *C. coli* was identified in 35.5% of chicken samples (30.2% in Poland). The results of the present and previous 5-year surveys demonstrated that the prevalence of *Campylobacter* in broiler carcasses has markedly decreased (from 70.6% in 2009 to 52.6% in 2018). At the same time, the percentage of *C. coli*-positive samples among all tested increased almost twofold (from 18.9% in 2009 to 34.5% in 2016), whereas the prevalence of *C. jejuni* decreased from 38.6% (2009) to 18.8% (2016).

Several studies documented that *C. jejuni* was more often isolated from chickens and chicken meat than *C. coli* (Boysen, Vigre, & Rosenquist, 2011; Deckert et al., 2010; Economu et al., 2015; EFSA &

ECDC, 2018; Gharbi et al., 2018; Hue et al., 2011; Moran, Scates, & Madden, 2009). These differences ranged from 90.0% to 9.0% (Deckert et al., 2010) to 57.1% and 42.5% (Hue et al., 2011), respectively. However, there are also studies reporting *C. coli* to be the prevailing *Campylobacter* species among isolates of poultry origin (Marinou et al., 2012; Nobile, Costantino, Bianco, Pileggi, & Pavia, 2013; Suzuki & Yamamoto, 2009).

Some studies demonstrated that there was a significant seasonal increase in the prevalence of *Campylobacter* in broiler carcasses or chicken meat (Guerin et al., 2010; Habib, Samper, Uyttendaele, Berkvens, & De Zutter, 2008; Jore et al., 2010). This seasonal variation in *Campylobacter* colonization in broilers can be explained as being temperature-related or associated with the presence of flies, which play the role of a bacterial vehicle in the warm months (Guerin et al., 2010). Furthermore, these differences could reflect levels of environmental contamination due to the more regular ventilation of poultry houses in summer which results in increasing contact with the outside environment (Nylen et al., 2002). During the present study, no significant increase in the presence of *Campylobacter* in broiler carcasses in relation to the warmer months was observed. On the contrary, a higher percentage of positive samples was identified during the autumn–winter period (peak in December) as compared to the summer months. This high percentage of *Campylobacter*-positive samples could be a result of low number of chickens tested; however, the prevalence rates obtained in each month were connected with fixed confidence intervals (95%) that show the result with the same certainty/accuracy.

The results of the present study highlighted that *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* of chicken carcass origin presented high resistance rates to ciprofloxacin (92.0% and 93.9%, respectively), nalidixic acid (90.3% and 93.8%, respectively), and to a lesser extent, to tetracycline (64.8% and 75.3%, respectively). Such a high prevalence of quinolone-resistant *Campylobacter* isolates in chickens may be due to the broad use of enrofloxacin (fluoroquinolone) in poultry production (Iovine, 2013).

Table 3
Antimicrobial multiresistance profiles of *C. jejuni* isolated from chicken carcasses.

Antimicrobial resistance profile	No. (%) of isolates					
	2014 (n = 101)	2015 (n = 136)	2016 (n = 86)	2017 (n = 104)	2018 (n = 98)	2014–2018 (n = 525)
CIP + STR + TET	1 (1.0)		2 (2.3)		1 (1.0)	4 (0.8)
CIP + NAL + STR + TET	10 (9.9)	20 (14.7)	19 (22.1)	26 (25.0)	19 (19.4)	94 (17.9)
CIP + NAL + ERY + TET	3 (3.0)					3 (0.6)
CIP + NAL + GEN + TET	1 (1.0)			1 (1.0)		2 (0.4)
CIP + NAL + ERY + STR + TET	1 (1.0)					1 (0.2)
CIP + NAL + GEN + STR + TET		1 (0.7)			1	2 (0.4)
CIP + NAL + ERY + GEN + STR + TET		1 (0.7)	1 (1.2)			2 (0.2)
Total	16 (15.8)	22 (16.2)	22 (25.6)	27 (26.0)	21 (21.4)	108 (20.6)

CIP, ciprofloxacin; STR, streptomycin; TET, tetracycline; NAL, nalidixic acid; ERY, erythromycin; GEN, gentamycin.

Table 4
Antimicrobial multiresistance profiles of *C. coli* isolated from chicken carcasses.

Antimicrobial resistance profile	No. (%) of isolates					
	2014 (n = 147)	2015 (n = 148)	2016 (n = 158)	2017 (n = 137)	2018 (n = 148)	2014–2018 (n = 738)
CIP + NAL + ERY + TET	4 (2.7)	4 (2.7)	5 (3.2)	3 (2.2)	2 (1.3)	18 (2.4)
CIP + NAL + GEN + TET	1 (0.7)					1 (0.1)
CIP + NAL + STR + TET	26 (17.7)	24 (16.2)	36 (22.8)	20 (14.6)	33 (22.3)	139 (18.8)
CIP + NAL + ERY + STR + TET	3 (2.0)	8 (5.4)	3 (1.9)	4 (2.9)	7 (4.7)	25 (3.4)
CIP + NAL + GEN + STR + TET	1 (0.7)					1 (0.1)
CIP + NAL + ERY + GEN + STR + TET			1			1 (0.1)
Total	35 (23.8)	36 (24.3)	45 (28.5)	27 (19.7)	42 (28.4)	185 (25.1)

Abbreviations as in Table 3.

According to a recent European Medicines Agency (EMA) report, in 2016 in Poland 9.7 mg for population correction unit (PCU) of fluoroquinolones in veterinary medicine were sold, which was much higher than average for the other 30 European countries (2.7 mg/PCU) (EMA, 2018). As shown in a recent European Union report on antimicrobial resistance, a high resistance level to ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid in *C. jejuni* isolates from broiler meat was reported, i.e. 63.4% and 61.9%, respectively (EFSA & ECDC, 2019). These percentages were lower than identified in the present study for the years 2014–2018 (92.0% and 90.3%, respectively). The resistance rates of *C. coli* obtained in the current investigation were even higher, i.e. 86.9% and 85.2% for CIP and NAL, as reported in the EFSA & ECDC report, respectively. Such high resistance rates to quinolones, especially to ciprofloxacin, is important from a public health point of view because CIP is considered to be one of the two critically important antimicrobials for the treatment of *Campylobacter* infections in humans (WHO, 2019).

Erythromycin is the drug of choice for the treatment of *C. jejuni* infections in humans. In the present study, there was a difference in the resistance to this antimicrobial between *C. jejuni* (1.1%) and *C. coli* (6.4%), and both rates were higher than the corresponding values obtained in the previous investigations during 2009–2013, i.e. 4.0% and 0.9%, respectively (Wieczorek & Osek, 2015). However, these differences were not as obvious as has been identified in other studies (Han et al., 2016; Pergola et al., 2017; Torralbo et al., 2015). On the other hand, another investigation in Poland revealed the higher percentages of *C. jejuni* than *C. coli* isolates from poultry meat resistant to erythromycin (3.0% and 1.7%, respectively), although this difference was not statistically significant (Andrzejewska, Szczepańska, Śpica, & Klawe, 2015). Several other studies demonstrated that *C. coli* display a higher resistance than *C. jejuni*, irrespective of the source where the isolates were obtained (Economou et al., 2015; EFSA & ECDC, 2019; Han et al., 2016; Pergola et al., 2017; Torralbo et al., 2015), although there are also opposite results (Fraqueza et al., 2014; Lapiere et al., 2016).

Previous studies performed in Poland and in other countries also revealed that *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* of poultry meat origin were highly resistant to ciprofloxacin (Wieczorek, Denis, & Osek, 2015, 2018, 2013; Andrzejewska et al., 2015; Fraqueza et al., 2014; Gharbi et al., 2018; Han et al., 2016; Nobile et al., 2013). It has been suggested that the broad use of fluoroquinolones in veterinary medicine can select for resistance and results in the high persistence of resistant *Campylobacter* isolates in the food chain (Garcia-Migura et al., 2014; Ge et al., 2013).

Multiantimicrobial resistance, defined as resistance to antimicrobials from three or more different classes, was more common among *C. coli* (25.1%) than *C. jejuni* (20.6%) isolates, respectively. Such differences were previously observed in our own studies (Wieczorek et al., 2013; 2015) and investigations performed by other authors (Fraqueza et al., 2014; Torralbo et al., 2015; Pergola et al., 2017). However, the multiresistant rates were either lower than those obtained in the present studies, e.g. 3.5% (Bailey et al., 2019) or much higher, i.e. 83.3% and 93.8% of isolates (Han et al., 2016; Torralbo et al.,

2015). There are also reports showing that more *C. jejuni* than *C. coli* displayed resistance to more than three classes of antimicrobials (Economou et al., 2015; Gharbi et al., 2018). A level of multi-antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolates of chicken origin is probably connected with the wide use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine, which generates a high level of such isolates ((Alfredson and Korolik, 2007)). Although antibiotics have been abandoned for use as growth promoters in animals, they are still applied, especially quinolones, for therapeutic treatment in chickens; thus, resistant *Campylobacter* strains are still present in poultry and poultry meat products (Smith & Fratamico, 2010).

5. Conclusion

The results of the present study show a relatively high level of contamination of chicken carcasses with *Campylobacter* in Poland during 2014–2018. The prevalence of these bacteria has not markedly changed during the study period, and was similar to the previous investigation performed during 2009–2013. Unlike many other investigations, *C. coli* was predominant over *C. jejuni*, covering 31.2% and 22.2% of isolates among 2,367 samples tested, respectively. The marked antimicrobial resistance to quinolones and tetracycline of *Campylobacter* from chicken carcasses identified over the last 10 years calls for the necessity to reduce the use of antimicrobials in the poultry treatment, and for the implementation of specific control procedures to decrease the level of contamination of chicken carcasses by campylobacters.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kinga Wiecek: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. **Łukasz Bocian:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Jacek Osek:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107159>.

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